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Research Article

Assessment And Evaluation of Black Cumin Seeds Tablet for Various Pharmacological Activity

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ABSTRACT

Black cumin seed tablets are supplements made from the seeds of *Nigella sativa*; a plant known for its medicinal properties. Black Cumin seeds is a natural substance. It is used to treat conditions such as antioxidant, Anti- inflammatory, anticancer, Antidiabetic symptoms. Tablets are the solid dosage Form containing medicament or medicaments, usually circular in shape and may be flat or Biconvex. Tablets are prepared by the compression method and hence call the compressed tablet. There are different types of tablets. Tablets are easy to administered and maintain the accuracy of Dosage form. Black Cumin seeds were found to possess various beneficial constituent like Alkaloids, phenolics, saponins and volatile compounds are prepared by wet granulation method. Further experiment on evaluation of different extraction Methods in order have herbal drugs like black Cumin seeds free net been used to treat various diseases. This Includes pre- formulation, formulation and evaluation black cumin tablets.

INTRODUCTION

Black cumin seeds (*Nigella sativa*) been used in traditional medicine for centuries due to their Wide range of therapeutic properties. Their pharmacological activities are attributed to the presence of bioactive compounds, such as Thymoquinone, alkaloids, saponins and essential fatty acids, among others. These compounds contribute to a wide range of medicinal benefits, including, antioxidant, anti-inflammator,

Antimicrobial, hay fever, digestive aid, cardioprotective antidiabetic, and anticancer effects.[1] In addition to the pharmacological testing, it is essential to assess the physical and chemical Properties of the Black Cumin seed tablets. With increasing interest in herbal medicine, Black Cumin seed tablets have gained popularity as a convenient dosage form to deliver these beneficial compounds.

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These tablets offer a convenient way to support overall wellness. Traditionally used in various cultures for boosting immunity, improving digestion, and promoting respiratory health, Black Cumin Seeds Tablets are now gaining global recognition as a holistic addition to daily health routines. Whether you're looking to enhance your natural defenses or support metabolic balance, this supplement brings centuries of herbal wisdom into modern health practices. When formulated into tablet form, black cumin seeds provide a convenient way to access these benefits in a concentrated dose.[2] Tablets are the solid dosage form containing medicament or medicaments, usually circular in shape and may be flat or biconvex tablets are prepared by the compression method and hence call the compressed tablet.

1.2 Advantages of Tablet

1. They are easy to be dispensed.
2. These are more stable dosage form.
3. They maintain the accuracy of dosage.
4. Bitter and nauseous substances can be given easily in tablet form after giving a suitable coating to the tablets.
5. They are the lightest and the most compact of all dosage forms.
6. Of all the dosage form, tablets are easiest and the cheapest as regard packing and transport.

7. They are better suited to a large-scale production as compared with any other unit oral dosage form.

1.3 Disadvantages of Tablet

1. Some drugs resist compression into tablet form due to their amorphous nature or low-density character.
2. Bitter tasting drugs, drugs with objectionable odour or drugs that the sensitive to oxygen or atmospheric moisture may require encapsulation or a special type of coating which may increase the cost of the finished tablets.
3. Drugs with poor wetting and slow dissolution properties are difficult to convert into tablets which provide full drug bioavailability.
4. The tablets cannot be used in case of emergency cases, because the rate at which active ingredient reaches the site to be treat slow.
5. Bioavailability of some drugs may be low due to poor absorption from the gastric tract.

PLANT PROFILE

1. Black Cumin seeds

Table no. 1. Plant profile of Black Cumin Seeds

Synonyms	Black caraway, nutmeg flower, Roman coriander, nigella, kalonji.
Biological source	Black cumin seeds are derived from the plant <i>Nigella sativa</i> .
Family	Ranunculaceae
Geographical distribution	Southwest Asia, India, Pakistan, North Africa, and parts of the Mediterranean. It is also cultivated in regions of Central Asia, Eastern Europe, and Southeast Asia.
Category	Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory, Anti-cancer, Hay Fever, Digestive Aid, Cardioprotective, Antidiabetic, Antimicrobial.

Side effects	Allergic reactions, stomach upset, low blood pressure, and interact with medications like blood thinners and diabetes drugs.	
Chemical Constituents	A) Linoleic Acid B) Oleic Acid C) Palmitic Acid D) Fatty Acid E) Thymoquinone	F) Potassium G) Proteins H) B1 (thiamine), B3 (niacin), B6 (pyridoxine) I) Nigellicine, Nigellimine

Fig.no.1 Black cumin Seeds

Fig.no.2 Black Cumin Seeds Powder

Health Benefits of Black Cumin Seeds

1. **Anti-inflammatory properties:** Thymoquinone, the main active compound in black cumin seeds, has strong anti-inflammatory effects, which may help with conditions like arthritis or asthma.
2. **Antioxidant effects:** These seeds help neutralize harmful free radicals in the body, potentially lowering the risk of chronic diseases.
3. **Boosts immune system:** Regular use may enhance immune function, helping the body fight off infections.[5]
4. **Supports heart health:** They may help reduce blood pressure, lower cholesterol levels, and improve blood lipid profiles.
5. **Regulates blood sugar:** Some studies show black cumin seeds can help maintain healthy blood glucose levels, which is beneficial for people with diabetes.
6. **Antimicrobial and antifungal:** They exhibit antibacterial and antifungal effects, potentially helping treat infections like Candida.
7. **Digestive health:** Traditionally used to relieve bloating, indigestion, and gas.
8. **Supports liver function:** May protect the liver from toxins and support its overall function.
9. **Skin and hair benefits:** Applied topically or taken as oil, it may help with acne, eczema, and promote hair growth.[6]

2. Ginger

Synonyms	Zingiber officinale
Biological source	The biological source of ginger is the rhizome of the plant Zingiber officinale, which is a flowering plant.
Family	Zingiberaceae
Geographical distribution	India, China, Indonesia, Thailand, Vietnam, Nigeria, Ethiopia, Ghana, Cameroon, Jamaica, Brazil, Peru, United States (Hawaii, Florida), Australia.
Category	Ginger helps prevent nausea, digestive issues, inflammation, colds, and may support heart health and reduce migraines.
Side effects	Ginger may cause stomach upset, diarrhea, allergic reactions, blood thinning, or lowered blood pressure in some people.[7]
Chemical Constituents	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Gingerol Shogaol 2. Zingiberene 3. Curcumin 4. Phenolic compounds 5. Essential oils

Fig.no.3 Ginger

Fig.no. 4 Acacia

Fig.no. 5 lactose

Fig.no.6 Magnesium Stearate

Fig.no. 7 Starch

Fig.no. 8 Talc

PRE-FORMULATION STDIES

$$H= 3\text{cm}, r= 4\text{cm } \Theta = \text{Tan-1 } \frac{3}{4} ,$$

1. Angle of repose: Angle of repose is defined as the maximum angle possible between the Surface of pile of powder and the horizontal plane, $\text{Tan } \theta = h/r$.

$$= \text{Tan-1}(0.75).$$

Angle of Repose: By using Formula, $\Theta = \tan^{-1} h/r$

2. Bulk Density: Bulk density of a powder is defined as the ratio of the mass of the powder and its bulk volume.[10]

Bulk density:

M= 10gm,

V=30ml Formula using,

Bulk density= mass of powder/ bulk volume

$$= 10/30$$

$$= 0.33$$

3. Tapped density: The tapped density is an increased bulk density attained after mechanical Tapping of container the sample. The inter particular interaction influence bulking properties and Interface with powder flow.

Tapped density M= 10gm, Vo=22ml Formula using, Tapped density= mass of powder/ tapped volume

$$= 10/22$$

$$=0.45$$

4. Porosity: whether the powder is porous or non-porous the total porosity expression for the calculation Remains Same. The percent porosity is Express as % porosity = (bulk volume- tapped volume) x100/ bulk Volume.

Porosity Formula using,

$$\% \text{porosity} = (\text{bulk volm} - \text{tapped volm}) \times 100 / \text{bulk volume}$$

$$= 30-22/30 \times 100$$

$$= 33.33\%$$

1. Carr's Index: Carr's Index an indication of the compressibility of powder. It is calculated by The Formula:

Carr's index = tapped density -bulk density /tapped density x100 Carr's using Index & Formula,[12]

Carr's Index = tapped density – bulk density/ tapped density

$$= 0.45 - 0.33 / 0.45 \times 100$$

$$= 26.66\%$$

2. Hausner Ratio: The Hausner Ratio is a number that is correlated to the flowability of a powder or Granule material. The Hausner Ratio is calculated by the Formula,[13]

$H = \rho_T / \rho_B$ Where,

ρ_B = bulk density of the powder.

ρ_T = tapped density of the powder. Hausner Ratio:

$$H = \rho_T / \rho_B$$

$$= 0.45 / 0.33$$

$$= 1.36$$

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Table no. 3. Formulation Table

Sr No.	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	Roles
1	Black Cumin seeds	5gm	5gm	5gm	Antimicrobial, hay fever, digestive aid, cardioprotective, including boosting immunity, antidiabetic, anticancer, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects.
2	Ginger	1gm	1gm	2 gm	Helps to prevent: nausea, digestive issues, inflammation, colds.
3	Acacia	1gm	1.5gm	1gm	Binder
4	Lactose	1gm	1.5gm	0.5 gm	Diluent
5	Magnesium stearate	1gm	0.5gm	1 gm	Lubricant
6	Starch	QS	QS	QS	Binder
7	Talc	1gm	0.5gm	0.5gm	Glident

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Generally herbal preparations are known for its “No side effect” property. The results of this

Project are that formulation and of black Cumin seeds Tablet perform Successfully.

Table no.4. Result and Discussion

Sr No.	Evaluation Test	F1	F2	F3
1	Shape of Tablet	Circular	Circular	Circular
2	Appearance	Uniform texture	Uniform texture	Uniform texture
4	Disintegration Test	30	32	32
5	Dissolution Test	50%	70%	60%
6	Hardness Test	2.8	3	3.7
7	Friability Test	0.650	0.771	0.589

Black cumin seed tablets are supplements made from the seeds of *Nigella sativa*; a plant known for its medicinal properties. These seeds contain compounds like thymoquinone, which are believed to have antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial effects. Black cumin seed tablets are commonly used to support immune health, improve digestion, and reduce inflammation. Some studies also suggest they may help with conditions like asthma, allergies, and diabetes. However, it's important to consult a healthcare

professional before using them, especially for specific health concerns.

CONCLUSION

I have been concluded that herbal drugs rather than used in synthetic drug which May have various side effects herbal drug may not have side effect as synthetic drug. Black Cumin seeds were found to possess various beneficial compounds. The antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anti-diabetic,

anti-cancer, activities observed in black Cumin seeds could be due to the presence of various detected. Pre-formulation studies on the powder included measuring its angle of repose, bulk density etc. The findings confirmed that the particles were not freely flowing. So, the compression of drugs Was executed by using wet granulation method. The tablets hardness, weight variation, friability, Disintegration time and dissolution were all evaluated. The findings confirmed that formulations Were employed effectively inside the clinical method of rapid-dissolving drugs. Magnesium Stearate become the fine remarkable disintegration for the formulation of black Cumin seeds Further Experiment on evaluation of different extraction methods in order have herbal drugs like black Cumin seeds Have been used to treat various diseases. The functional properties observed in the extract obtained from black Cumin seeds are beneficial for pharmaceutical, food and feed industries. For instance, Further experiments on evaluation of different extraction methods in order to have herbal Drug like black Cumin seeds can used to treat various diseases. From this study I came to know the various additional Uses of black Cumin seeds and the technique of performing formulation of black Cumin seeds tablet.

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